

ActIVO: An Active perception framework for skill transfer through Iterative Visual Observations

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Abstract— Learning by demonstration (LbD) through visual observation is widely used in literature for tackling the problem of robot programming. However, identification and exact localization of the point of interest (e.g. human hand) during the demonstration, in most of the cases, comes with a non-negligible uncertainty, introduced by the detection algorithm and the sensor characteristics. In this work, we propose an active perception framework for gaining the maximum information during iterative demonstrations performed by a human, towards LbD. The method considers an in-hand camera and it is based on a covariance weighted pseudo-inverse estimator that accounts for the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the sensor. The proposed framework, coined as “ActIVO”, is experimentally validated in two scenarios, utilizing a UR5e robotic manipulator and an in-hand RealSense RGB-D camera.

I. INTRODUCTION

Explicit robot programming has been utilized in industrial settings for many decades. Despite the recent advancements in associated technological tools offered by robot manufacturers, explicit programming remains both technically demanding and time-intensive. These requirements become significantly more challenging when the robot has to operate in unstructured environments, such as in agricultural applications, where its motion must be adaptable to varying targets and environmental geometries, while often involving motion patterns that are difficult to define analytically. A pertinent example is the task of fruit picking, where the robot must execute precise motions to detach the fruit from the plant’s branch. In this context, the fruit’s position, orientation, and size can vary on each occasion, while the manipulation for detachment often involves intricate motions. The latter can be difficult to program explicitly and may differ for each fruit, underscoring the need for more flexible and adaptive robotic programming approaches.

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Learning by Demonstration (LbD), was recently proposed for tackling the problem of robot programming. According to LbD, the motion is taught to the robot based on a set of motion demonstrations [1], [2]. In most of the cases, these motion demonstrations are performed by a human and they are captured either utilizing proprioceptive data (e.g. robot encoders), when the robot is physically guided by the human-teacher [3], [4], or through external sensors, e.g. by visually observing the motion using a camera [5], [6]. Although LbD through visual observations is more intuitive and less cognitively and physically demanding for the human-teacher, it incorporates a relatively larger uncertainty, due to sensor noise, estimation errors and/or possible occlusions [7]. It is worth noting that, in the current literature, such LbD methods utilise only passive observations of the task, i.e. a static camera is considered.

Active perception (or “Active vision”, when a camera sensor is considered) is a notion introduced to tackle the problem of maximizing the information gained regarding an object of interest [8]–[10]. Active perception is inspired by biological systems, like humans, which intentionally act in order to acquire information, rather than relying on passive observations. Active perception methods have been utilized across various domains, including industrial [11], [12] and agricultural sectors [13], [14], as well as in robotic manipulation through reinforcement learning [10]. Some of the active perception controllers are based on the perceived geometry of the environment [14]–[16], while others employ machine learning for finding the optimal policies [13], [17], or even movement primitives models [11]. While active perception finds application across a wide range of tasks, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, it has not previously been explored for addressing the problem of LbD through active observation of human behavior.

In this context, our present work considers the case in which the motion of a point on the human hand (e.g. fingertip) is taught to the robot through iterative visual observations of demonstrations performed by a human-teacher. Such a task could involve the manipulation of a fruit for picking it, i.e. harvesting without a cutting tool, in which the farmer could transfer their life-long experience by performing a number of demonstrations with the robot observing their actions. The action is observed using an in-hand camera, i.e. a camera attached to the end-effector of the robot. Given the uncertainty involved in the 3D-position estimate provided by the visual sensor, we aim at iteratively minimizing the

uncertainty of the gathered information related to the motion executed by the tips of the human fingers. Gathering the maximum information, and consequently minimizing the uncertainty related to the trajectory followed by the human-hand, plays a crucial role on the learning performance and could significantly reduce the number of iterations required for skill transfer. To achieve this, we propose an active perception framework, based on a covariance weighted pseudo-inverse estimator.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND CONCEPT SOLUTION

Let us consider a robotic system with an in-hand RGB-D camera, i.e. a camera attached to its end-effector. Let $\{C\}$ be the frame of the camera and $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be the joint variables of the robot, with $n \geq 6$ being the number of its joints. Further, let the robotic system be kinematically controlled, i.e. accepting joint velocity commands $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c(t)$. Our aim is through multiple iterative demonstrations, to move the camera such that the total uncertainty of the gathered information related to the position of the human fingertip is minimized. Furthermore, we consider that the uncertainty characterizing the camera (visual sensor) measurements is not homogeneous with respect to the frame of the camera.

The mapping between the generalized velocity of $\{C\}$ and the joint velocities are given by:

$$\mathbf{v}_c = \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})\dot{\mathbf{q}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times n}$ is the Jacobian matrix of the robot and $\mathbf{v}_c \triangleq [\dot{\mathbf{p}}_c^T \ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_c^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the generalized velocity with $\mathbf{p}_c, \boldsymbol{\omega}_c \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the position of the camera and its angular velocity respectively.

Let $\mathbf{p}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the actual position of the fingertip with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ its estimate provided by the camera utilizing a specific human hand detection algorithm; as depicted in Fig.1. The estimation error is then given by $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf} - \mathbf{p}_{cf}$. Let $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c \triangleq \text{var}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \in S_{++}^3$ be the variance-covariance matrix of the probability distribution¹ of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$. Note that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c$, not only captures the accuracy and characteristics of the sensor, but also incorporates errors introduced by the detection algorithm. We assume that an estimate of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c$ is either directly available or can be statistically extracted from a sufficiently large dataset of measurements.

In the context of human hand tracking with an RGB-D sensor, while the human hand is reliably tracked in the $x-y$ plane of the camera (i.e. the pixel space of the camera's RGB output), the estimation of depth often involves considerable uncertainty, mainly due to the sensitivity and low robustness of the depth estimation mechanism. In particular, the distance estimation can be affected by external infrared exposure, such as sunlight (in case the RGB-D camera uses an infrared pattern), the reflective properties of the material, or even the color of the object. Moreover, most RGB-D cameras employ a spatial low-pass smoothing filter for depth information, introducing further error into depth measurement.

¹A normal distribution is considered.

Fig. 1: Uncertainty of the camera estimation.

Taking into account all these factors, we consider the uncertainty of the measurement along the z -axis of the RGB-D camera to be higher than that along the other axes. Consequently, we assume the estimated covariance matrix for the RGB-D camera with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$, to be as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_d \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the variance of the measurement along the x and y axes, while $\sigma_d > \sigma \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the variance along the z axis of the camera. Note that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c$ is assumed to be constant, as it reflects the characteristics of the camera with respect to its frame. Let $\mathbf{p}_c(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_c(t) \in SO(3)$ be the position and orientation (expressed in a rotation matrix form) of the camera, respectively, w.r.t. the inertial frame $\{0\}$. Further, let $\mathbf{p}_f(t) = \mathbf{p}_c(t) + \mathbf{R}_c(t)\mathbf{p}_{cf}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the actual position of the fingertip in time and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) = \mathbf{p}_c(t) + \mathbf{R}_c(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be its estimate captured by the camera in a single observation with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$, with $t \in [0, T]$ and $T \in \mathbb{R}^+$ being the duration of the demonstration. The covariance matrix of the estimation error of the camera with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$ is then given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(t) = \mathbf{R}_c(t)\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_c\mathbf{R}_c^T(t). \quad (3)$$

It is therefore easily inferred, given the above rationale and assumptions, that the motion can not be perfectly or even accurately captured and/or reconstructed by a single observation, and that multiple observations from different viewpoints would contribute to the improvement of the reliability of the measurements.

Our goal is to estimate the position of a moving human fingertip, i.e. $\mathbf{p}_f(t)$, following an iterative procedure, in which the total uncertainty of the estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$ is minimized in each iteration. To achieve this, we propose a novel framework including a) a covariance weighted least square estimator [18] based on multiple demonstrations of the same task performed by the human and captured by the camera, and b) a novel active perception control policy that moves the camera on-line, such that the uncertainty of the total captured data is minimized. The proposed control scheme aims at yielding a gradually more homogeneous and lower total uncertainty (given the current and the previous captured data) along the axes of \mathbb{R}^3 . In other words, our goal is to make the eigenvalues of the total covariance matrix gradually equal, for all $t \in [0, T]$, given that the human performs a number of motion demonstrations of the same task, in order to increase the quality of motion reconstruction.

III. MOTION RECONSTRUCTION FROM MULTIPLE OBSERVATIONS

Given that m demonstrations of the same task are performed by the human, let $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the estimated position of the fingertip captured by the camera in the i -th iteration, where $t \in [0, T_i]$ with $T_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$ being the duration of the i -th demonstration, $i = 1, \dots, m$. Let the field of view of the camera be different in each iteration, a condition that will be ensured by the active perception controller detailed in the next Section. Also, let $\mathbf{p}_{c,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t) \in SO(3)$ be the position and the rotation matrix, respectively, of the camera during the i -th iteration (observation). In order to exploit the multiple demonstrations of the task, we must synchronize the trajectories. To achieve this, one can consider the first iteration as the reference one and synchronize the others by searching for the closest position of this trajectory to the task-space estimate of each iteration, given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t) = \mathbf{p}_{c,i}(t) + \mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,i}(t), \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are the estimated position of the fingertip with respect to the camera's frame $\{C\}$ and the inertial frame $\{0\}$, respectively. Therefore, and for simplicity of the presentation, for the rest of the paper, consider $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,i}(t)$, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,i}(t)$, $\mathbf{p}_{c,i}(t)$, $\mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t)$ be the temporally scaled variables. Hence, for the rest of the paper, $T_i = T, \forall i = 1, \dots, m$.

In order to exploit the multiple observations and the knowledge (or estimate) of the covariance matrix of the camera measurement, we propose the utilization of a covariance weighted least square estimator. Based on this estimator, the estimate of the position of the fingertip, after the completion of the m -th iteration is obtained from:

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) = \mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}}(t) \left(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}(t) \right), \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B}(t) \triangleq \text{diag} \left(\mathbf{R}_{c,i}^{\top}(t) \right) \in \mathbb{R}^{3m \times 3m}, i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_c(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{c,1}(t) \\ \mathbf{p}_{c,2}(t) \\ \dots \\ \mathbf{p}_{c,m}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,1}(t) \\ \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,2}(t) \\ \dots \\ \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,m}(t) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}}(t) \triangleq (\mathbf{A}^{\top}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^{\top}\mathbf{W}, \quad (8)$$

the covariance weighted left pseudo-inverse of \mathbf{A} with

$$\mathbf{W} \triangleq \mathbf{I}_m \otimes \Sigma_c^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m \times 3m}, \quad (9)$$

$\mathbf{I}_m \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ the identity matrix, " \otimes " denoting the Kronecker product (i.e. \mathbf{W} is a block diagonal matrix with Σ_c^{-1} in each block-element of its main diagonal) and

$$\mathbf{A}(t) \triangleq [\mathbf{R}_{c,1}(t) \ \mathbf{R}_{c,2}(t) \ \dots \ \mathbf{R}_{c,m}(t)]^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^{3m \times 3}. \quad (10)$$

Lemma 1. *The covariance of $\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}$ is equal to \mathbf{W}^{-1} .*

Proof. For $\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}$ it holds:

$$\text{var}(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}) = \text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}), \quad (11)$$

as $\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t)$ is considered free of any uncertainty. After taking into account $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf} = \mathbf{P}_{cf} + [\varepsilon_1^{\top} \ \varepsilon_2^{\top} \ \dots \ \varepsilon_m^{\top}]^{\top}$, where $\varepsilon_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the estimation error in the i -th iteration, (11) becomes:

$$\text{var}(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}) = \text{var} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \dots \\ \varepsilon_m \end{bmatrix} \right) = \mathbf{I}_m \otimes \Sigma_c = \mathbf{W}^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

□

Remark 1. *Equation (5) gives the weighted least square solution of the following system:*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_{c,1}^{\top}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) &= \mathbf{R}_{c,1}^{\top}(t)\mathbf{p}_{c,1}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,1}(t), \\ \mathbf{R}_{c,2}^{\top}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) &= \mathbf{R}_{c,2}^{\top}(t)\mathbf{p}_{c,2}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,2}(t), \\ &\dots \\ \mathbf{R}_{c,m}^{\top}(t)\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t) &= \mathbf{R}_{c,m}^{\top}(t)\mathbf{p}_{c,m}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf,m}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

with respect to $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$. Notice that (13) yields after multiplying with $\mathbf{R}_{c,i}^{\top}(t)$ both sides of (4) for every iteration i . In particular, as the solution is weighted using the inverse of the covariance matrix of the camera, (5) gives the solution of the system (13), by assigning greater significance to the axis in which the covariance of the measurement is lower.

Proposition 1. *The total covariance matrix of the estimate computed from (5), after the data accumulation of m iterations, is given by:*

$$\bar{\Sigma}_m(t) = (\mathbf{A}^{\top}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{A})^{-1} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \Sigma_i^{-1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

where $\Sigma_i(t) \triangleq \mathbf{R}_{c,i}(t)\Sigma_c\mathbf{R}_{c,i}^{\top}(t)$ is the individual covariance matrix of the i -th iteration with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$.

Proof. Taking into account (5), the covariance of the estimate after the m -th demonstration is the following:

$$\bar{\Sigma}_m(t) \triangleq \text{var}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)) = \mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}} \text{var} \left(\mathbf{B}(t)\mathbf{P}_c(t) + \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf} \right) (\mathbf{A}^{\mathcal{L}})^{\top}. \quad (15)$$

After substituting (8) and applying Lemma 1 to (15), we get (14). □

To provide insight into how the total covariance of measurements, $\bar{\Sigma}_m$, changes with each new iteration-demonstration, a numerical example is presented in Fig. 2 for two scenarios. In the first case (left column of Fig. 2), two observations are considered, and the ellipsoids of the individual covariance of the two demonstrations are orthogonal, i.e. $\Sigma_1 \perp \Sigma_2$. Notice that in this ideal case, the resulted total covariance $\bar{\Sigma}_2$ (after the 2nd iteration), is already homogeneous (spherical). In the second case (right column of Fig. 2), three observations are considered, with the ellipsoids of the individual observations not being orthogonal

to each other. Notice that, in this more realistic case, the resulted total covariance $\bar{\Sigma}_3$ (after the 3rd iteration), tends also to be homogeneous.

Fig. 2: An example of two orthogonal observations and that of multiple observations.

IV. PROPOSED CONTROL SCHEME

Let us assume that the user performs the $(m + 1)$ -th demonstration. In this case, the total covariance matrix of the data, accumulated through the previous m iterations, is given by (14). Let, $\mathbf{n}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$ be the eigenvector of $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t)$ with largest corresponding eigenvalue, for a given $t \in [0, T]$, i.e. its major axis. Our control objectives are two:

- 1) To align the axis of the camera having the lowest uncertainty (minor axis, i.e. the sensor's most reliable axis), denoted by $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, with \mathbf{n}_d . In essence, we seek to minimize uncertainty along the axis where the current total uncertainty is maximum, or, put more simply, we aim to observe the scene from the viewpoint where uncertainty is highest, given all previous observations.
- 2) To keep the fingertip at the center of the field-of-view of the camera as much as possible and the distance of the camera from the fingertip equal to d , where $d \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is the nominal constant observation distance, which is dependent on the minimum distance that the camera can provide depth estimation.

To this end, and given the mapping given in (1), we propose the following control law, in the form of commanded joint velocities, which is composed by the superimposition of two intermediate control signals, \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 , one for each control objective respectively:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c \triangleq \mathbf{J}^\dagger(\mathbf{q}) (\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{v}_2), \quad (16)$$

where

$$\mathbf{v}_1 \triangleq k_a \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{R}_c \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}) \\ \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{n}_d) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (17)$$

Fig. 3: Depiction of control signal $\mathbf{v}_1 + \mathbf{v}_2$.

is the intermediate control signal for aligning (reaching) the minor axis of the covariance of the camera (Σ_{m+1}) to the major axis of the total covariance of the currently gathered data ($\bar{\Sigma}_m$), and

$$\mathbf{v}_2 \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_c & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{R}_c \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} k_p (\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}\| - d) \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}}{\|\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}\|} \\ k_o \mathbf{u}([0 \ 0 \ 1]^\top, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^6 \quad (18)$$

is the intermediate control signal for centering and maintaining the distance d from $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}$. In (16)-(18), $k_a, k_p, k_o \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are positive tunable gains, while

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \triangleq \text{acos} \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}^\top \mathbf{b}}{\|\mathbf{a}\| \|\mathbf{b}\|} \right) \frac{\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{b}}{\|\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{a})\mathbf{b}\|} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \quad (19)$$

indicates the minimum rotation (in angle-axis form) between any two vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{S}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the skew-symmetric matrix, and $\mathbf{J}^\dagger \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 6}$ a pseudoinverse (the inverse, if $n = 6$) of $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})$.

To get a better understanding of the rationale behind the design of the control signal, Fig.3 illustrates the action of the two intermediate control signals, \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 . Note that \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 act as virtual velocities on the robot's end-effector (in-hand camera). In particular, \mathbf{v}_1 acts as a virtual velocity that simply pivots the camera around the point of interest, utilizing reaching control, in order to align \mathbf{n} to \mathbf{n}_d . The translation part of \mathbf{v}_2 is a control signal that guides the camera's position to a distance of d from the point of interest. Note that the translation parts of \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 are orthogonal, and therefore their action is not affected by each other. The rotational part of \mathbf{v}_2 attracts the z -axis of the camera towards the vector pointing to the point of interest, for attracting the latter towards the center of the field of view. Notice that the equilibrium of the rotational part of \mathbf{v}_1 is also an equilibrium for the rotational part of \mathbf{v}_2 .

Remark 2. Note that \mathbf{v}_1 induces a simple first order attractor, which does not involve the rate of change of the major axis $\mathbf{n}_d(t)$. Therefore, although this part of the control scheme is expected to asymptotically converge for a constant \mathbf{n}_d , its performance is affected when $\dot{\mathbf{n}}_d(t) \neq \mathbf{0}$.

Hence, although $\mathbf{n}(t)$ is attracted to $\mathbf{n}_d(t)$, in general, a non negligible error is expected to exist between $\mathbf{n}(t)$ and $\mathbf{n}_d(t)$.

Remark 3. Note that the considered covariance matrix of the camera, given in (2), even when expressed w.r.t. the inertial frame, has two same minimum eigenvalues equal to σ . Consequently, determining \mathbf{n} is not straightforward. In this case, one has to select a vector that belongs to the plane defined by the two minor eigenvectors of this matrix.

V. THE PROPOSED COMPLETE LBD FRAMEWORK

Lastly, we integrate the motion reconstruction mechanism and the control scheme presented above in a unified Learning by Demonstration framework, available at the following github repository: <https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/ActiVO>, which is presented in Algorithm 1.

The complete framework involves multiple iterations of demonstrations, whose number can be either predefined, or determined by reaching a target uncertainty level, as shown in Algorithm 1. As a measure of the current uncertainty level, the volume and/or sphericity of the ellipsoid of the total covariance, i.e. $\bar{\Sigma}_m$, could be utilized. Furthermore, in the first iteration (see the “if $i = 1$...” conditions in Algorithm 1), only \mathbf{v}_2 is active for centering and maintaining the distance from the point of interest, as no previous demonstrations are available. Finally, we designate the reference time variable t_r from the first demonstration, which serves as the reference trajectory for synchronizing all time series.

After the calculation of the complete trajectory estimate $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t_r)$ (at the end of the algorithm), an one-shot encoding mechanism can be utilized to encode the motion based on this estimate. Such a mechanism could be the Dynamic Movement Primitives model [19], [20].

VI. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The proposed framework was evaluated experimentally utilizing a UR5e robotic manipulator with an Intel RealSense D415 RGB-D camera attached to its end-effector. For the kinematics of the robot, the Python version of the *Robotics toolbox* [21] was utilized. The frame rate of the camera was set to 30 fps and the control cycle of the robot was set to 2 ms. For the human hand detection and localization, the “Mediapipe Hands” [22] algorithm was employed, pre-trained with a sample of 16,000 real and 100,000 artificially generated human hand images. The hand detection algorithm and the control loop were running on different threads to ensure that the timing of the control loop remained unaffected.

For evaluating the framework, two experiments were conducted, the first considering a simple path of pre-determined geometry on a flat surface, and the second considering a fruit picking operation. In each iteration, an audio cue, signifying the initiation of the demonstration, was provided to the human, triggered as soon as the human hand was perceived by the camera. The y -axis of the camera was selected to represent \mathbf{n} (based on Remark 3) and the camera’s initial pose for each iteration was selected to be roughly orthogonal to the previous view-point of the camera. To synchronize signals across iterations, we identified the closest point on

Algorithm 1 Proposed LbD framework

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1: Inputs:  $\Sigma_c, d, dt$  ▷ Camera and robot properties
2: Select values for:  $k_a, k_p, k_o$ 
3: for each demonstration  $i$  do
4:    $t := 0$  ▷ Initialization
5:   while  $t_r < T_r$  do
6:     Get  $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{R}_c, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})$ 
7:     Get  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}$  from camera
8:      $t := t + dt$ 
9:     if  $i = 1$  then ▷ 1st iteration
10:       $t_r := t$ 
11:       $\mathbf{v}_1 := \mathbf{0}_6$  ▷ No prev. demos
12:      Calculate  $\mathbf{v}_2$  from (18)
13:       $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t_r) := \Sigma_i$  ▷ Initialization
14:    else
15:      Find the corresponding  $t_r$  of the 1st demo.
16:       $\mathbf{n}_d :=$  major eigenvector of  $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t_r)$ 
17:      Calculate current  $\Sigma_i$  from (3)
18:       $\bar{\Sigma}_m(t_r) := \left( \bar{\Sigma}_m^{-1}(t_r) + \Sigma_i^{-1} \right)^{-1}$  ▷ Eq. (14)
19:      Calculate  $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2$  from (17), (18)
20:    end if
21:    Calculate  $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c$  from (16)
22:    Command  $\dot{\mathbf{q}}_c$  to the robot
23:    Store  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{cf}$  as a sequence of  $t_r$ 
24:    Store  $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{R}_c$  as a sequence of  $t_r$ 
25:    Store  $\bar{\Sigma}_m$  as a sequence of  $t_r$ 
26:    if  $i = 1$  AND user commands break then
27:       $T_r := t_r$ 
28:      Break
29:    end if
30:  end while
31:  if Target uncertainty reached then
32:    Break
33:  end if
34: end for
35: Define  $\mathbf{W}$  from (9)
36: Calculate  $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{P}_c, \hat{\mathbf{P}}_{cf}$  from (10), (6), (7)
37: Calculate  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f$  sequence from (5) ▷ Estimator
38: Train an encoding mechanism (e.g. a DMP), based on
    the  $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f$  sequence of  $t_r$ 

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the trajectory of the first iteration (considered the reference trajectory) to the current position of the robot, within a window of 500 samples ahead in time. For facilitating this procedure a first order low-pass IIR filter² with a cutoff frequency of 5 rad/s was applied to the reference trajectory.

Since the lower end of the camera’s depth range is ~ 25 cm, the nominal observation distance was set at $d = 0.3$ m, while the other parameters of the framework were specified as $k_p = k_a = 1, k_o = 2, \sigma = 0.001$ and $\sigma_d = 0.05$. At the end of the procedure, the reconstructed trajectory, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$, was encoded using a Dynamic Movement Primitives

²The low-pass filter was utilized only for the synchronization and not for the final motion estimation.

Fig. 4: Experimental setup for (a) hand movement along a pre-defined elliptical path, and (b) fruit picking emulation.

(DMP) model, involving 20 Gaussian kernels; the evolution of the DMP is denoted by $\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$.

A video containing footage from these experiments can be found in https://youtu.be/0_M8fTugfyY.

A. Hand movement along a simple pre-determined path

The first experiment considered a simple task, where the human was instructed to move his hand along an annotated segment of an ellipse, drawn on a flat surface, as depicted in Fig. 4a. For this experiment, the position of the tip of the subject's index finger was designated as the point of interest. The experiment involved two iterations/observations of the task, as the sphericity of Σ_2 was deemed already sufficient for the signal reconstruction after the second iteration.

The path perceived by the camera in each iteration ($\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t)$), as well as the reconstructed one, based on ActIVO, motion ($\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$) and the time evolution of the DMP model ($\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$) are depicted in Fig. 5. Notice the smoothness of the estimated trajectory, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$, and the encoded trajectory, $\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$, as compared to the individually perceived trajectories in each iteration ($\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t)$).

To provide insight into how the total covariance of measurements, $\bar{\Sigma}_m$, changes with each new iteration-demonstration, the covariance ellipsoids of each iteration (Σ_1, Σ_2), as well as the total one after the two iterations ($\bar{\Sigma}_2$), are depicted in Fig. 6 for a random time instance $t_r = t_1$ (t_r represents the synchronized common for all iterations). Notice how the considered total uncertainty (after iteration 2), represented by the ellipsoid of $\bar{\Sigma}_2$, is approximately spherical, having significantly less volume (i.e. less uncertainty) than the ones reflected by the perceived data during the first and second iterations.

B. Fruit picking emulation

The second experiment considered the emulation of a fruit picking operation, utilizing a mock-up setup with a plastic fruit (see Fig. 4b). For this experiment, the position of the tip of the thumb of the human was the designated point of interest, as the emulated scenario involved detaching the fruit by applying pressure to the branch with the thumb. As with the previous experiment, this case involved two iterations/observations of the task.

Fig. 5: Motion reconstruction for the experiment involving the pre-determined ellipsoidal path.

Fig. 6: Covariance ellipsoids for $t_r = t_1$.

The path of the thumb perceived by the camera in each iteration $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t)$, as well as the proposed reconstructed motion $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t)$ and the time evolution of the DMP model $\mathbf{p}_{dmp}(t)$, are depicted in Fig. 7, while Fig. 8 shows the corresponding coordinates in time. A notable spike in the perceived position is evident in the first iteration (blue line) around $t_r \approx 1.2$ s, primarily attributed to an error in the camera's depth estimation. It is important to highlight that relying solely on a single observation from one viewpoint, such as that of the first iteration, would result in significantly erroneous thumb position estimates, potentially exhibiting high rates or even discontinuities. However, the proposed method effectively eliminates this spike by taking into account data from the second iteration and considering the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the sensor in the estimation process, in particular the fact that the error predominantly occurs along the z -axis of the camera during the first iteration. Indeed, the dotted line in Fig. 7 depicts the estimated trajectory without axis weighting based on covariance, i.e. by simply computing the mean of the perceived trajectories, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_f(t_r) = 0.5(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,1}(t_r) + \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{f,2}(t_r))$. It is worth noting how this approach is influenced by the spike at $t_r \approx 1.2$ s.

Fig. 7: Motion reconstruction for the fruit picking emulation experiment.

Fig. 8: Time evolution of observations, estimate (based on ActIVO) and DMP model.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In the context of Learning by Demonstration through visual observations, we have proposed ActIVO, an active perception framework for minimizing the uncertainty during iterative demonstrations performed by a human. The framework considers an eye-in-hand visual sensor and it is based on a covariance weighted pseudo-inverse estimator, based on an estimate of the non-homogeneous uncertainty of the visual sensor. The proposed framework is experimentally evaluated in two scenarios. The experiments clearly demonstrate the improved motion reconstruction performance attained by utilizing ActIVO, as compared to a single-shot reconstruction or a non-weighted pseudo-inverse estimation. In the future, the utilization of Extended and/or Unscented Kalman Filters (EKF and UKF respectively) will be investigated in order to exploit the Dynamical Movement Primitive model trained

based on the previous demonstrations.

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